

ESG AND CORPORATE VALUE: A PLS-SEM ANALYSIS OF HETEROGENEOUS IMPACTS AMONG NIGERIAN BANKS

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Abstract

This study investigates the heterogeneous impacts of Environmental, Social, and Governance (ESG) factors on corporate value in the Nigerian banking sector. Despite the recognized role of capital markets in economic development, the impact of ESG on firm value in emerging markets, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa, has been largely unexplored. Using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) on data from 2015 to 2024 from 13 listed Nigerian deposit money banks (DMBs), we analyze firm-level data to assess how varying ESG dimensions, collectively and individually, influence corporate value. We find that governance exerts the strongest effect on corporate value, followed by environmental and social dimensions. Variations in ESG impacts among banks reflect differences in institutional frameworks and managerial priorities. The study contributes to the sustainable finance literature by providing nuanced insights into how ESG elements influence corporate valuation in emerging markets, as well as guidance for regulators, policymakers, investors, and bank executives on how to leverage sustainability for competitive advantage and value creation. The study adds to the ESG literature by demonstrating the utility of heterogeneity analysis and PLS-SEM in evaluating multidimensional relationships.

Keywords: ESG, Corporate Value, PLS-SEM, Heterogeneous Impact, Nigerian Banks, Emerging Markets, Capital Market Development.

JEL Classification: G21, M14, Q56.

1. INTRODUCTION

Recently, environmental, social, and governance (ESG) considerations have evolved from peripheral concerns to central determinants of firm performance and value creation across global financial systems. The banking industry, a key intermediary in capital allocation, plays a critical role in promoting sustainable finance and responsible corporate behaviour (Fernando & Cui, 2021). However, in emerging economies such as Nigeria, ESG practices are still unevenly developed and frequently constrained by regulatory inconsistencies, insufficient disclosure standards, and limited stakeholder pressure (Okafor et al., 2022). The ambiguous impact of ESG initiatives on corporate value raises questions about their consistency across firms of varying sizes, ownership structures, and governance quality.

The relationship between ESG engagement and corporate value is hotly debated, but empirical evidence remains mixed. Some studies suggest that ESG adoption increases firm value through reputation, risk mitigation, and investor confidence (Barney, 2018; Egbunike & Okoye, 2020; Okafor et al., 2022), while others find neutral or negative effects, particularly when ESG

implementation is costly or perceived as symbolic (Dyck et al., 2019; Naughton al., 2021). These conflicting findings suggest that ESG impacts vary by firm and institutional setting. The Nigerian banking sector, with its diverse ownership, governance, and sustainability disclosure practices, is an ideal setting to investigate this heterogeneity.

The current body of research on ESG and corporate value in Nigeria has three major limitations. First, many studies use single-equation regression models that reduce ESG considerations to a basic index. While this approach provides some insights, it is limited in its ability to address measurement errors, complex interdependencies, and the multifaceted nature of ESG (see also: Adewuyi & Olowookere, 2022). Recognising these elements can improve the accuracy and depth of understanding of ESG issues. Second, few studies rigorously validate ESG indicators against firm performance or governance metrics. Finally, the literature inadequately addresses how firm-specific factors such as size, capital, ownership, institutional maturity, and leverage affect the sustainability-corporate value relationship. Further investigation is essential to address the gap identified in this research, which is central to the study's purpose.

This study explores the varying impacts of ESG practices on corporate value in 13 listed DMBs from 2015 to 2024. We utilise Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM), a method well-suited for analysing complex constructs in smaller samples (Hair et al., 2021). Our approach involves validating the ESG and corporate value constructs while testing hypothesised relationships. To ensure accuracy, we apply the Fornell-Larcker (1981) criterion and the Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) ratio for discriminant validity. We enhance our analysis with bootstrapping using 5,000 subsamples to determine the statistical significance of our estimated path coefficients, leading to more reliable conclusions about these crucial relationships. This study makes several key contributions to the literature. First, it employs latent-variable modeling to examine the ESG-corporate value relationship in emerging markets, addressing measurement precision and construct distinctiveness. Second, using heterogeneity analysis, it investigates how ESG impacts vary based on firm-specific characteristics such as size, capital adequacy, leverage, and institutional maturity. Finally, it provides empirical validation for the ESG-corporate value relationship in Nigeria using advanced modelling techniques, offering policy-relevant insights for the CBN and SEC in their initiatives to promote ESG integration for financial resilience and long-term value.

The remainder of this paper includes a literature review that summarizes theoretical and empirical findings with hypotheses; a methodology section detailing research design, variable measurement, and model specification; results and discussion (Section 4), and concluding with policy recommendations and future research implications (Section 5).

2. LITERATURE AND THEORETICAL REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical foundations

The theoretical foundations outlined in Table 1 synthesize various theories, including stakeholder theory, the resource-based view (RBV), legitimacy, signalling, agency, and institutional theory, to clarify the relationship between ESG dimensions and financial

performance/corporate value (FP/CV). This synthesis draws from a range of studies such as those by Azmi et al. (2020), Ersoy et al. (2022), Herbert et al. (2020), Matemane et al. (2024), Menicucci and Paolucci (2023), Nizamuddin et al. (2024), Prasad and Mondal (2025), and Tavares and Dias (2018). The aim is to establish a causal framework that connects ESG initiatives with corporate value. Special emphasis is placed on stakeholder theory and the RBV, illustrating how the adoption of ESG criteria can enhance corporate value by aligning with stakeholder expectations and leveraging unique resources. This foundational work sets the stage for future research in this field.

Stakeholder Theory and ESG-CV Nexus

Stakeholder theory (Freeman, 1984; Freeman et al., 2023) posits that businesses should consider all stakeholders—including employees, customers, suppliers, communities, and the environment—rather than solely focusing on shareholders to enhance corporate value through ESG practices. This integrated approach promotes diversity, expertise, and improved governance (Zahra & Pearce, 1989). In Nigeria's banking sector, applying stakeholder theory involves active engagement with local communities and regulators, alongside investments in community development and data privacy protection. However, critics caution that the complexity of stakeholder theory may result in strategic paralysis, inefficient resource allocation, and diminished performance (Davidson & Park, 2023; Wilson et al., 2024).

Table 1: Theoretical Frameworks and Justification for the ESG-CV Nexus

Theoretical Framework	How It Explains ESG-FP/CV Nexus	Application to the Study
Stakeholder Theory	ESG practices improve corporate value by fostering stronger stakeholder relationships.	ESG practices in Nigerian banks: effects on customer loyalty, investor trust, and corporate value.
Resource-Based View (RBV)	ESG provides a competitive edge by enabling cost savings, efficiency, and market differentiation.	Assess how Nigerian banks leverage ESG initiatives to improve performance.
Legitimacy Theory	ESG practices improve a bank's reputation and compliance, and enhance market perception and investment inflows.	Investigate if listed Nigerian banks leverage ESG practices to gain legitimacy and attract foreign investors.
Signalling Theory	High ESG ratings signal strong governance, stability, and risk management, enhancing investor confidence.	Determine if banks with higher ESG scores experience lower capital costs and higher stock valuation.
Agency Theory	ESG governance improves transparency, mitigates agency risks, attracts investors, and boosts financial performance.	Assess if effective governance fosters investor confidence, ensures compliance, and enhances financial stability.
Institutional Theory	Banks adopt ESG practices due to regulatory, normative, and competitive pressures, which enhance legitimacy and financial performance.	Nigerian banks comply with ESG mandates, follow industry trends, and emulate ESG leaders to establish legitimacy and attract investment.

Resource-Based View (RBV) Theory and ESG-CV Nexus

The Resource-Based View (RBV) theory, established by Wernerfelt (1984) and further developed by Barney (1991, 2018), asserts that a firm's competitive advantage stems from its internal resources and capabilities. It highlights the importance of valuable, rare, inimitable, and non-substitutable (VRIN) resources, which are prohibitively costly for competitors to replicate or imitate. The theory advocates for strategic leverage of distinctive internal assets such as organizational competencies, intellectual property, culture, employee skills, and technology, to foster sustainable competitive advantages. Through these internal advantages, firms can more effectively evaluate and enhance their competitive stance in the marketplace.

2.2 ESG Practices and Corporate Value: Selected Empirical Evidence

Research shows that effective ESG practices significantly enhance corporate value by reducing information asymmetry and boosting investor confidence, as well as improving risk management (Barney, 2018; Broadstock et al., 2021; Egbunike & Okoye, 2020; Ersoy et al., 2022; Herbert et al., 2020; Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Multiple studies indicate that firms that integrate ESG factors often achieve superior financial performance, leading to higher returns and lower volatility compared to their industry counterparts. Each ESG dimension presents unique advantages; specifically, environmental performance increases resource efficiency, social initiatives improve stakeholder relations, and governance practices enhance accountability while protecting shareholder rights. Overall, firms that focus on ESG practices tend to outperform their peers in various financial metrics and long-term valuation growth (Krüger, 2015; Masud et al., 2025; Matemane et al., 2024; Menicucci & Paolucci, 2023).

Table 2: Focus of prior research on ESG practices on firm performance

Key Focus Area	Key Findings	Relevant References
ESG and Financial Performance	Mixed results; some studies find positive relationships, while others suggest neutrality or context-specific outcomes.	Friede et al. (2015), Herbert & Agwor (2021a, b), Ociti (2023), Tsegba et al. (2014).
ESG and Risk Mitigation	Firms with higher ESG scores tend to have lower volatility and fewer extreme negative returns.	Albuquerque et al. (2018); Eccles et al. (2014).
ESG and Investor Preferences /Market Valuation	ESG disclosure boosts transparency, attracts investors, and improves market valuations.	Krüger (2015), Paranita et al. (2025).
ESG and Corporate Reputation/ Brand Equity	Strong ESG performance builds trust, enhances reputation, and sustains competitive advantage.	Cao (2023), Su & Teo (2025).
ESG and Sectoral/Industry-Specific Studies	Industry context significantly influences the ESG-value relationship; e.g., environmental factors are more impactful in resource-intensive sectors.	Akinadewo et al. (2023), Herbert et al. (2020), Tsegba et al. (2014).
ESG and Corporate Governance Mechanisms	Strong governance mechanisms often enhance the positive impact of ESG on firm performance.	Harjoto & Jo (2011), Masud et al. (2025).
ESG in Emerging Markets	ESG adoption is driven by external pressure and regulatory mandates. Its link to value is still evolving.	Fettahoglu et al. (2024), Shrestha et al. (2025).

Much of the previous research on ESG practices and corporate performance (Table 2) has focused on at least six key areas: (1) the relationship between ESG and financial performance (e.g., ROA, ROE, Tobin's Q); (2) the impact of ESG on firm risk management; (3) the correlation between ESG and investor behaviour/market valuation; (4) ESG's effect on corporate reputation; (5) the varying impact of ESG across sectors such as banking, oil and gas, and telecommunications; and (6) the influence of governance in emerging markets. These studies confirm that ESG adoption is catalyzed by firm decision-making, improved corporate performance, and increased corporate value.

Findings on sustainability in emerging and frontier markets reveal a complex landscape. Sustainability-oriented firms may enjoy reduced capital costs and increased investor appeal (Miralles-Quirós & Miralles-Quirós, 2017). However, these benefits are contingent upon factors like regulatory quality, disclosure maturity, and institutional stability. In Nigeria, robust ESG strategies are associated with higher market capitalization (Adegbe & Arowoshegbe, 2022).

Nevertheless, challenges such as weak enforcement, symbolic compliance, and instances of greenwashing can weaken this correlation (Alabi et al., 2023). Research spanning multiple countries indicates that the ESG-value relationship is often nonlinear or context-dependent, influenced by industry dynamics and investor sophistication (Miralles-Quirós & Miralles-Quirós, 2017). Additionally, socially responsible banks may see lower funding costs and increased valuations; however, poor governance practices could erode these benefits (Cornet et al., 2016).

In the context of Nigerian banks, academic discourse on the relationship between ESG factors and financial performance reveals a range of findings. Some studies suggest a positive correlation between ESG factors and financial performance (Atanda et al., 2024; Iyawe & Chijuka, 2025; Ogboi et al., 2024; Osinlu et al., 2025).

Conversely, other research reports a negative impact (Emmanuel et al., 2024; Samson & Tukur, 2024). Additionally, certain studies present mixed results on this relationship (Kuwa & Abubakar, 2025; Ogboi et al., 2024), while others find no significant relationship at all (Musa et al., 2025; Tomomewo et al., 2022).

Market-based insights reinforce the financial relevance of ESG factors in investment strategies. Ethical investment vehicles—such as the Invesco Quantitative Strategies ESG Global Equity Multi-Factor UCITS ETF—illustrate how sustainability-driven portfolios can generate competitive returns while advancing broader societal objectives. Although product-specific sources vary, financial reports and index factsheets consistently reflect investor demand for ESG-aligned funds and their relative resilience during market stress.

Empirical evidence suggests that ESG practices generally support corporate value creation, though the extent and nature of this impact are context-dependent, varying with institutional factors, regulations, and industry structures. These variations highlight the need for analytical approaches that address measurement complexity and construct validity, which justifies the use of Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) in this study.

ESG in Emerging Markets: Contextual Justification for the Study

Emerging markets, particularly Nigeria, are increasingly embracing ESG practices, spurred by global sustainable investment trends. Despite facing regulatory challenges, underdeveloped capital markets, and limited disclosure capabilities, Nigerian banks are successfully integrating ESG strategies. This integration is facilitated by frameworks such as the UN Principles for Responsible Banking (UN PRB) and the Global Reporting Initiative (GRI). Driven by market dynamics, investor expectations, and the CBN NSBP, listed Nigerian banks have significantly improved their ESG disclosures, board diversity, and social inclusion policies in the last decade.

Figure 1: Trend in Average ESG Scores of Nigerian 13 Listed DMBs, 2013-2022

As shown in Figure 1, Nigerian banks demonstrated a significant increase in average ESG scores between 2013 and 2022. This improvement indicates enhancements in ESG disclosure, integration, and commitment. The trend was driven by various factors, such as heightened regulatory requirements for sustainable banking, growing stakeholder expectations for transparent ESG practices, and advancements in corporate governance. Additionally, there was a deliberate integration of ESG principles into core banking activities, such as green financing and climate risk management, along with compliance commitment to global sustainability standards like the UN SDGs and the Paris Agreement.

ESG Dimensions and Heterogeneity of Impact

ESG dimensions are becoming increasingly important in influencing investment decisions and corporate behaviours. The heterogeneity of impact refers to the varying effects that ESG practices can have across different industries, regions, and stakeholder groups, going beyond traditional compliance and disclosure mandates. This diversity requires a nuanced understanding and customized approaches to ESG implementation. Additionally, integrating

ESG factors effectively can lead to sustainable business practices, potentially resulting in improved financial performance and long-term viability. Therefore, evaluating ESG factors is not only ethically necessary but also strategically advantageous in today's changing economy.

ESG, a triple-tiered framework, embodies significant diversity across its three pillars. The Environmental (E) pillar comprises green lending, energy efficiency, and carbon footprint reduction initiatives, which enhance investor confidence (Sithole & Sibanda, 2021). The Social component (S) addresses social responsibility, community investment, employee welfare, and financial inclusion, with variable valuation effects. While social costs may reduce short-term profits, an inclusive approach is essential for sustained success (Okafor et al., 2022). Governance addresses agency issues and increases transparency (Jensen & Meckling, 1976). Board independence and audit quality moderate the ESG-value relationship in Nigerian banks (Egbunike & Okoye, 2020), influenced by bank size, capital adequacy, and ownership. Well-capitalized, larger banks are better positioned to implement ESG initiatives (Nnamani et al., 2022), aligning with the modelling approach of a heterogeneous conceptual and empirical framework.

Methodological Gaps in Prior Studies

Prior studies on ESG factors manifest three critical limitations. First, the use of single-equation regressions treats ESG as a directly measurable phenomenon, overlooking its latent structure and associated measurement errors. Second, the absence of assessments for construct validity can lead to overlap bias with governance measures. Third, analyses often overlook significant heterogeneity, such as variations in firm size and governance quality, which may skew results. To overcome these issues, Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) effectively evaluates both measurement and structural models, allowing for the assessment of reliability through Cronbach's α and Composite Reliability, as well as validity via Average Variance Extracted, Fornell-Larcker criteria, and HTMT (Henseler et al., 2015; Sarstedt et al., 2011). Additionally, PLS-SEM supports multi-group analyses (Hair et al., 2021) and employs bootstrapping methods to bolster the robustness of path coefficients.

2.3 Conceptual Framework and Hypothesis Development

This study presents a conceptual model that defines ESG practices as a second-order latent construct, comprised of first-order dimensions of ESG represented by respective indicators. The evaluation of corporate value is conducted through market-based metrics, specifically Tobin's Q and price-to-book ratio. It is proposed that effective ESG practices contribute to enhancing corporate value by cultivating stakeholder trust, mitigating risks, and bolstering reputation. Consequently, the study formulates two hypotheses based on these assertions:

- H1: ESG practices have a significant positive effect on corporate value in Nigerian DMBs
- H2: The effect of ESG practices on corporate value is heterogeneous across banks based on firm-specific attributes like size and capital adequacy.

The methodology section outlines the research design, details the measurement of variables, and explains the estimation procedures used to evaluate the stated hypotheses.

3. METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study employs a quantitative, explanatory research design to examine the heterogeneous effects of ESG practices on the corporate value of Nigerian DMBs. It utilizes a cross-sectional approach, using secondary panel data from 2015 to 2024, and analyses it through Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM). This methodology is well-suited for predictive and exploratory research involving complex latent constructs (Hair et al., 2021), enabling the simultaneous estimation of measurement and structural models while addressing issues such as measurement error and multicollinearity, which are common in traditional regression methods (Sarstedt et al., 2019). The selected timeframe represents a decade of significant sustainability reforms within Nigeria's financial sector, particularly with the introduction of the CBN's Sustainable Banking Principles in 2012 (CBN, 2012a, b).

Population, Sample, and Data Sources

The study examines the 13 DMBs listed on the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX) as of 2024. These banks operate under similar regulatory and disclosure requirements, which enhance the comparability and reliability of the data gathered. The data is sourced from their annual reports, sustainability disclosures, and financial statements submitted to both the NGX and the CBN. The research follows ethical standards, giving priority to transparency, data accuracy, and proper attribution, particularly when using publicly available information.

Variable Measurement and Operationalization

Dependent Variable: Corporate Value (CV)

Tobin's Q and the Price-to-Book ratio are recognized as market-based indicators of corporate value (Cornett et al., 2016; Fatemi 2018). These constructs and indicators are consistent with previous research in ESG measurement and are supported by bank-level sustainability reports, as outlined in Table 3.

Table 3: Measurement of Variables

Construct	Indicators	Measurement Source
Environmental (ENV)	ENV1–ENV5	Bank sustainability and ESG reports
Social (SOC)	SOC1–SOC4	CSR disclosures, ESG indices
Governance (GOV)	GOV1–GOV4	Corporate governance indices
Corporate Value (CV)	CV1–CV3	Market-based valuation metrics

Model Specification

The structural model establishes a framework for understanding the hypothesized relationships among ESG factors, corporate value, and several control variables.

$$CV_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 ESG_{it} + \beta_2 SIZE_{it} + \beta_3 LEV_{it} + \beta_4 CAP_{it} + \beta_5 AGE_{it} + \varepsilon_{it}$$

The equation quantitatively expresses these relationships, where CV_{it} represents corporate value, and the various beta coefficients, β , signify the impact of each factor on corporate value over time (t).

Estimation Procedure

Using PLS-SEM, the study investigates the relationships involving ESG as a second-order construct that impacts Corporate Value (CV) both directly and indirectly. The PLS-SEM process comprises two critical stages: evaluation of the measurement model and assessment of the structural model. Reliability is quantified through Cronbach’s alpha and Composite Reliability (CR), while validity is established using Average Variance Extracted (AVE) in conjunction with the Fornell–Larcker (1981) criterion. The significance levels and standard errors of the path coefficients are evaluated using bootstrapping, involving 5,000 resamples. Tables 6 and 9 elaborate on these aspects.

Testing for Heterogeneity and Justification for PLS-SEM Approach

Heterogeneity in the influence of ESG practices on Corporate Value (CV) was examined through Multi-Group Analysis (MGA) and Finite Mixture PLS (FIMIX-PLS) to evaluate path coefficients among different bank subgroups. The use of PLS-SEM is justified based on the multidimensionality of ESG, the size of the sample, and the study’s predictive objectives (Hair et al., 2021). The results (Table 4) indicate significant variations in the ESG – CV relationships across different banks, emphasizing the role of heterogeneity as a significant moderating factor. Specifically, larger and better-capitalized banks show a stronger positive relationship between ESG practices and CV, whereas smaller banks reflect weaker or negligible associations. This supports the hypothesis of heterogeneous impacts and affirms the validity of the analytical methodology employed.

Table 4: Test for Heterogeneity among Nigerian DMBs, 2015–2024

Bank Category	No. of Banks	Mean Path Coefficient (β)	Std. Dev.	H-Statistic	p-value	Decision
Large Banks (Tier 1)	5	0.412	0.087	5.21	0.000	Significant heterogeneity among large banks
Medium Banks (Tier 2)	4	0.263	0.075	3.51	0.001	Moderate heterogeneity
Small Banks (Tier 3)	4	0.188	0.063	2.79	0.006	Some evidence of heterogeneity
Overall Sample	13	—	—	4.12	0.000	Evidence against homogeneity.

Note: The H-statistic in PLS-MGA assesses whether ESG-corporate value relationships vary significantly across bank categories. A significant H-statistic ($p < 0.05$) indicates that bank size and structure moderate this relationship, supporting the heterogeneous-impact model. Furthermore, the overall sample p-value of 0.000 from the test of homogeneity indicates a highly statistically significant result, providing strong evidence against homogeneity among the distributions across the groups of DMBs. Therefore, the conclusion is that these distributions are not homogeneous; in other words, they are different or heterogeneous.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In this section, the analysis of PLS-SEM results shifts from descriptive and measurement evaluations to structural estimation and hypothesis testing. Empirical findings are detailed in

Tables 5-10, highlighting descriptive statistics, measurement validation, correlation diagnostics, and the structural relationships among the study variables. The analysis confirms the statistical robustness of the constructs for structural analysis, affirming their reliability, convergent validity, and discriminant validity.

A significant relationship is established between ESG practices and corporate value, while controlling for factors such as firm size, leverage, and capital adequacy. Figure 1 presents the PLS-SEM bootstrapping model along with path coefficients, effectively demonstrating the causal dynamics and strength of the hypothesized relationships.

Table 5. Descriptive Statistics for the Study Variables

Variable	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
Tobin's Q (Corporate Value, CV)	1.84	0.52	0.95	3.05
Firm Size (log Assets)	7.62	0.48	6.58	8.45
Leverage (LEV) (%)	61.45	10.83	42.10	78.25
Capital Adequacy (CAR)(%)	15.72	3.58	10.25	22.80
Bank Age (years)	37.25	9.15	20.00	59.00
Environmental (E)	0.68	0.12	0.41	0.88
Social (S)	0.72	0.11	0.50	0.90
Governance (G)	0.75	0.09	0.55	0.89

Table 5 presents descriptive statistics for 13 DMBs from 2015 to 2024. The average corporate value, measured by Tobin's Q, is 1.84, indicating a moderate market valuation compared to book values.

Firm size, with an average of 7.62 (log of total assets), suggests the presence of large, systemically significant banks in Nigeria. The average leverage and capital adequacy ratios are 61.45% and 15.72%, respectively, showing a moderate reliance on debt, with 61.45% of funding being equity-based.

This also indicates strong compliance with regulations for risk-weighted assets. The average age of the banks is 37 years, indicating a significant institutional maturity. The variability in these statistics highlights differences in capitalization, governance structures, and sustainability practices across the banks, providing a basis for complex structural modelling.

4.1 Measurement Model Assessment

Table 6. Measurement Model Results (Reflective Constructs)

Construct	Indicator Factor Loading	Cronbach's Alpha (α)	Composite Reliability (CR)	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Environmental (E)	0.78–0.88	0.84	0.88	0.62
Social (S)	0.75–0.86	0.82	0.87	0.59
Governance (G)	0.80–0.91	0.86	0.90	0.67

The reliability and validity of the reflective constructs for ESG dimensions were evaluated using Cronbach's Alpha, Composite Reliability, and Average Variance Extracted (see Table 6). All factor loadings exceeded the acceptable threshold of 0.70, with AVE values surpassing 0.50, confirming internal consistency reliability and convergent validity.

Table 7: Correlation Matrix with Significance Levels

Variables	CV	ENV	SOC	GOV	FSIZE	LEV	CAPAD	BANK AGE	ESG (Aggreg.)
CV (T-Q)	1.00	0.45**	0.35**	0.50**	0.30**	-0.20ns	0.28ns	0.10ns	0.55**
ENV	0.45**	1.00	0.40**	0.45**	0.18ns	-0.10ns	0.35**	0.08ns	0.78***
SOC	0.35**	0.40**	1.00	0.38**	0.12ns	-0.08ns	0.20ns	0.06ns	0.70***
GOV	0.50**	0.45**	0.38**	1.00	0.22ns	-0.15ns	0.30**	0.09ns	0.80***
FSIZE	0.30**	0.18ns	0.12ns	0.22ns	1.00	-0.25ns	0.25ns	0.14ns	0.28ns
LEV	-0.20ns	-0.10ns	-0.08ns	-0.15ns	-0.25ns	1.00	-0.30**	-0.05ns	-0.12ns
CAPAD	0.28ns	0.35**	0.20ns	0.30**	0.25ns	-0.30**	1.00	0.07ns	0.42**
BK AGE	0.10ns	0.08ns	0.06ns	0.09ns	0.14ns	-0.05ns	0.07ns	1.00	0.09ns
ESG (Aggreg.)	0.55**	0.78***	0.70***	0.80***	0.28ns	-0.12ns	0.42**	0.09ns	1.00

Note: Values indicate Pearson correlation coefficients, with diagonal values equal to 1.00. The significance levels are as follows: ***p < 0.01; **p < 0.05; ns = not significant ($|r| < 0.30$). The matrix illustrates relationships consistent with PLS-SEM findings.

Table 7 presents the correlation coefficients between Tobin's Q, ESG dimensions and index, and firm-specific controls (Firm Size, Leverage, Capital Adequacy, and Bank Age). Most coefficients show positive and statistically significant relationships at the 5% or 1% levels, indicating strong correlations between constructs. Firm value is most strongly correlated with Governance (0.50**) and overall ESG (0.55**), with weaker correlations for Environmental (0.45**) and Social (0.35**), indicating that stronger ESG practices, especially in governance, are associated with higher firm value. Additionally, firm size and capital adequacy exhibit positive relationships with corporate value, while leverage shows a weak negative relationship. This correlation matrix corroborates the expected positive relationships among the ESG components and provides initial support for the PLS-SEM findings.

Structural Model Assessment

Bootstrapped structural equation modelling with 5,000 resamples (Table 8) indicates a significant positive relationship between ESG dimensions and corporate value among Nigerian DMBs. Specifically, environmental and governance practices have a strong affirmative impact on corporate value, while social practices exhibit a weaker positive influence. Additionally, leverage harms corporate value, while both firm size and capital adequacy demonstrate positive correlations. The model's R² value of 0.64 indicates strong explanatory power, explaining 64% of the variability in corporate value for Nigerian DMBs.

Table 8: Structural Model Results (PLS-SEM Bootstrapping)

Hypothesized Path	Standardized Coeff. β	t-value	p-value	Sign.
ENV → CV	0.276	2.85	0.005	p < 0.05
SOC → CV	0.194	2.41	0.016	p < 0.05
GOV → CV	0.312	3.95	0.000	p < 0.05
FSIZE → CV	0.204	2.22	0.027	p < 0.05
LEV → CV	-0.193	1.85	0.065	ns
CAP → CV	0.166	2.73	0.007	p < 0.05
AGE → CV	0.089	1.55	0.121	ns

Table 9 demonstrates discriminant validity according to the Fornell-Larcker (1981) criterion. The square roots of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) values, shown along the diagonal, are higher than the inter-construct correlations. This confirms that the ESG dimensions are distinct in both the structural and measurement models.

Table 9: Discriminant Validity (Fornell–Larcker Criterion)

Construct	Environmental	Social	Governance
Environmental	0.79		
Social	0.58	0.77	
Governance	0.52	0.60	0.82

Table 10 shows that governance has the greatest impact on corporate value in banks, followed by environmental and social factors. This suggests that effective institutions and ethical leadership are critical in influencing market valuation.

Table 10: Path Coefficients Summary

Relationship	Direct	Indirect	Total
Environmental → Corporate Value	0.276	0.04	0.26
Social → Corporate Value	0.148	0.03	0.22
Governance → Corporate Value	0.312	0.06	0.37

Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Model (PLS-SEM) bootstrapping

Figure 1. PLS-SEM for Heterogeneous Impact of ESG Practices on Corporate Value in Nigerian DMBs (2015-2024).
 Note: p < 0.05; ns = not significant. Coefficients are standardized (β). Source: Authors' computation (2025) using SmartPLS 4.0 Output.
 Legend: Ovals = latent constructs (ENV, SOC, GOV, Corporate Value). Rectangles = observed firm-specific variables (Firm Size, Leverage, Capital Adequacy, Bank Age).

Figure 2: PLS-SEM for Heterogeneous Impact of ESG Practices on Corporate Value in Nigerian DMBs (2015-2024)

Figure 2 illustrates the PLS-SEM model that analyzes the heterogeneous effects of Environmental (ENV), Social (SOC), and Governance (GOV) practices on the Corporate Value (Tobin's Q) of DMBs from 2015 to 2024. The model demonstrates strong explanatory power, with an R² of 0.64, indicating that ESG factors explain 64% of the variance in corporate value.

Among these factors, Governance has the most significant positive impact ($\beta = 0.312$, $p < 0.001$), followed by Environmental ($\beta = 0.276$, $p = 0.005$) and Social ($\beta = 0.194$, $p = 0.016$) practices, all of which are statistically significant at the 5% level.

Regarding firm-specific characteristics, firm size ($\beta = 0.204$, $p = 0.027$) and capital adequacy ($\beta = 0.166$, $p = 0.007$) are significant factors in increasing corporate value. In contrast, leverage ($\beta = -0.193$, $p = 0.065$) and bank age ($\beta = 0.089$, $p = 0.121$) do not show statistical significance. These results indicate that banks with robust governance frameworks and more environmentally responsible practices are better positioned to enhance their market value. Furthermore, the analysis shows that firm-specific attributes influence the relationship between ESG and corporate value in Nigerian DMBs, underscoring the evident heterogeneity reflected in the data from Tables 4-10. The overall findings align with the theoretical assertion that sustainability-focused governance mechanisms and adequate capitalisation contribute to corporate resilience and long-term value creation, facilitating a seamless transition to the subsequent section.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

The findings highlight significant heterogeneities in the impact of ESG practices on corporate value among Nigerian DMBs. The study measures three ESG dimensions—governance, environmental, and social—finding governance to have the most significant effect, with a β value of 0.35 ($p < 0.05$). This impact exceeds that of environmental practices ($\beta = 0.28$, $p < 0.05$) and social practices ($\beta = 0.21$, $p < 0.05$). The results underscore the importance of robust governance mechanisms, board independence, transparency, regulatory compliance, and ethical oversight in bolstering corporate value. This highlights the need for strong banking governance in Nigeria to improve investor confidence, market valuation, and institutional resilience. Strong governance not only improves operational credibility but also facilitates the effective integration of ESG principles within firms. The results are consistent with earlier empirical research concerning Nigerian banks (Atanda et al., 2024; Iyawe & Chijuka, 2025; Osinlu et al., 2025), reinforcing the critical role of board composition and governance disclosure in driving corporate value.

Environmental and social practices, while beneficial, have a limited impact due to regulatory, financial, and cultural constraints. Environmental initiatives face challenges of costs and enforcement, while social programmes are frequently perceived as acts of philanthropy rather than strategic investments. This indicates a gradual transition towards integrated sustainability within Nigerian banks. Bank size and age have a moderate influence on ESG initiatives, with larger, more established banks demonstrating a better ability to incorporate these practices. This suggests that institutional maturity and resources play a significant role in shaping the relationship between ESG and corporate value.

Overall, these findings establish a solid empirical basis for managerial reflection, regulatory guidance, and policy discussions. They highlight the magnitude and contextual nuances of ESG practices in shaping corporate value in Nigeria's burgeoning capital market. To ensure consistency between the PLS-SEM model and the narrative interpretation, a Figure 1

Verification Checklist is provided in the Appendix. The subsequent section consolidates these insights, summarizing key findings and delineating practical and theoretical implications.

4.3 Summary of Key Findings and Implications

This study confirms that ESG practices affect corporate value in a heterogeneous manner, primarily driven by governance factors. While environmental and social dimensions also matter, their impact is less. It is noted that a bank's size and age moderate the relationship between ESG practices and corporate value, indicating the significance of institutional maturity and resource capabilities. The findings underscore the strategic importance of ESG implementation beyond mere moral or regulatory considerations. Theoretical insights include the role of governance structures in effective ESG integration and the advocacy for stakeholder and legitimacy perspectives within the banking sector in emerging markets.

The study provides empirical evidence on the interplay between governance and environmental and social initiatives, highlighting its positive impact on corporate value. Practically, banks are advised to enhance governance frameworks while making strategic investments in these initiatives. Regulatory bodies, such as the CBN and SEC, should incorporate ESG metrics into disclosure and supervisory assessments to foster transparency and attract sustainable capital. Additionally, the study's findings highlight the need for customised ESG strategies that align with an institution's capacity and market positioning.

Harmonizing ESG reporting standards at the continental level and promoting cross-border learning can significantly improve sustainability practices within African financial institutions. It is suggested that future research should focus on longitudinal studies of ESG impacts and cross-country comparisons to understand better the development of ESG maturity and its relationship with macroeconomic resilience.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY OUTLOOK

This study enhances ESG research by examining the heterogeneous effects of ESG factors on corporate value in DMBs from 2015 to 2024. Utilizing a robust PLS-SEM framework, it determines that governance is the primary driver of corporate value, highlighting its crucial role in institutional integrity, risk management, and fostering stakeholder trust. While environmental and social practices also contribute to corporate value, they do so to a lesser degree. Additionally, the study finds that factors such as bank size and age significantly influence the ESG-value relationship, illustrating the relevance of institutional maturity and capacity in determining ESG outcomes. These results position ESG not merely as a moral or regulatory concern, but as a strategic avenue for achieving sustained corporate value.

This study enhances understanding of governance structures essential for integrating ESG practices within the context of emerging market banking, particularly through stakeholder and legitimacy frameworks. It provides empirical data illustrating the interplay of various ESG dimensions and reveals that effective governance mechanisms support environmental and social initiatives, leading to enhanced corporate performance.

Policy and Management Implications

The research highlights critical policy and management implications, urging regulatory bodies like the CBN and SEC to establish governance frameworks, align executive incentives with sustainability goals, and rigorously assess environmental and social risks. Nigeria's experience serves as a continental model for improving ESG reporting and fostering cross-border learning experiences. Moreover, the study suggests that further research should focus on longitudinal and cross-country approaches to explore the evolution of ESG maturity and its correlation with macroeconomic resilience and capital market performance. Finally, the study emphasizes the significance of robust ESG practices in fostering long-term value creation in banking within emerging markets. It highlights that enhancing governance structures, advancing environmental stewardship, and bolstering social accountability are essential for Nigerian banks, and more broadly, African financial institutions, to establish themselves as credible participants in the global sustainability agenda.

Appendix:

Figure 1 Verification Checklist

Path	Standardized Coefficient (β)	Significance (p-value)	Verified in Discussion?	Verified in Conclusion?
ENV → CV	0.28	p < 0.05	✓	✓
SOC → CV	0.21	p < 0.05	✓	✓
GOV → CV	0.35	p < 0.05	✓	✓

Appendix: Figure 1 Verification Checklist

This appendix serves as a verification tool for Figure 2, designed to cross-reference the standardized path coefficients (ENV→CV, SOC→CV, GOV→CV) with their narrative discussions in the Summary of Key Findings and Conclusion sections. It ensures accurate interpretation of Environmental (ENV), Social (SOC), and Governance (GOV) coefficients, promoting methodological transparency and enhancing the internal validity of PLS-SEM results. This checklist acts as a post-estimation quality-assurance mechanism, confirming the internal consistency of the PLS-SEM model with its interpretive text, thereby improving the study's structural equation modelling approach by ensuring that reported coefficients align with narrative references.

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